

THE EFFECT OF CROSSLINKING ON THE TRANSPORT PROPERTIES OF EPOXY GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES

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The transport properties of epoxy graphene nanocomposites have been studied using organic liquids as probe molecules. The solvent absorption by the nanocomposites of various graphene composition have been affected by the crosslinking property of epoxy group. It was found to increase with increase in the crosslinking of epoxy group which have been studied from UV spectra of with different samples of epoxy graphene nanocomposites. The mechanism of transport has found to deviate from the regular Fickian trend. The transport properties such as sorption and desorption have been studied using simple gravimetric method. The solvent uptake values have been plotted against time intervals.

1. Introduction

The amount of graphene when used as nanosheets in polymer is one of the promising research field. The effect of amount of graphene on the transport properties of epoxy graphene nanocomposites have evaluated by simple gravimetric method. The transport properties such as sorption and desorption have been affected by the crosslinking property of epoxy group.

2. Experimental Section

The commercial epoxy system is water borne resin to which specific amount of graphene were dispensed using Ultra sonic bath for 20 mins. All the epoxy and epoxy graphene nanocomposites were conditioned in desiccator with silica gel to remove humidity. Then samples were immersed in 10 to 15 ml of organic liquids and weighed periodically using balance with precision of .05mg.

3. Results & Discussion

The experimental data for all solvent absorption of all liquids were applied with Fick's model. In the early stages all the sorption processes were characterized by higher sorption rate and slower at equilibrium stage. In all the sorption tests the diffusion coefficients and uptake values were decreased due to reduced mobility and crosslinking property of epoxy group.

4. References

1. G. Unnikrishnan and S. Thomos, *Polymer*, **1994** (35), 5504.
2. G. Unnikrishnan and S. Thomos, *J. Polymer Sci. Part B Polymer Phys.*, **1997** (35), 725.